

ASSESSING THE ROLE OF ACADEMIC REPRESENTATIVES WITH THE CHANGING TIMES AND RELEVANCE IN EDUCATION WORLD

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ABSTRACT

A person who has the capacity and tenacity to lead a team and achieve their goals while keeping the goals in mind is referred to as a leader. In today's competitive global environment, educational leaders must live and work in a global world that expects a lot of them, not only in terms of education but also in other areas. One of the most significant obstacles that educational leaders or teachers have is that they must respond to numerous queries.

When it comes to technology, the world has undergone a significant transformation. Focus on research and study all strategies to keep up with the expanding world of education. Innovative teaching technologies, modes of learning, and improving the ways through which lecturer needs to be supplied. There is much that can be done to improve students' learning outcomes, and this must be done at all levels of education, from elementary to higher education. The current study focuses on the changing needs and challenges that educational leadership faces in order to keep up with the changes, as well as their importance in developing leaders of tomorrow.

Key words: Learning, leadership, Educator, future leader

INTRODUCTION

A person who has the capacity and tenacity to lead a team and achieve their goals while keeping the goals in mind is referred to as a leader. In today's competitive global environment, educational leaders must live and work in a global world that expects a lot of them, not only in terms of education but also in other areas. One of the most significant obstacles that educational leaders or teachers have is that they must respond to numerous queries. When it comes to technology, the world has undergone a significant transformation. Innovative teaching technology, ways of learning and enhancing the ways through which lecturer needs to be given, focus on research and learn all methods to keep in track with the evolving world of education. A lot needs to be done to increase the students learning outcome and these needs to be done from small to higher level of education.

The role of an academicians is to make the student aware about what is happening around the world and to transform the individual with the latest happening around. With time, roles and

responsibilities change, but there is no denying that education is the sole weapon that can make things happen, and that things will happen for a valid and dependable cause, making this a noble vocation.

Things are changing, and they are changing rapidly, as a result of the advent of technology, which is why there is so much dissatisfaction and tension among the youth. There are many more obligations of today's educational leader that are not limited to teaching. There are other other obligations, such as administrative duties.

The challenges

Every academic institution's leader's primary goal should be to produce something that is centred on value. As this will aid in the formation of an individual. There are a number of persons in an institution, including the teaching faculty, and special attention should be paid to ensuring that all staff and other people are supporting the academic leader in their work. The job of employees is critical since academicians require their support in a variety of tasks. They can significantly improve the reliability and authenticity of teaching learning outcomes.

Because the academic leader is the person who will guide a country's future, he is a crucial component. Leading others has a critical part, as does taking responsibility for reaching the goal. The relationship with a student is more of a mentor, guide, and friend, with the goal of helping him comprehend and become more accountable. We cannot compromise on this crucial part of any nation's future since it lays the route for it.

An educator must strike a balance between his professional and personal commitments, since he may be forced to disregard his personal commitments owing to his professional obligations, therefore how he manages his responsibilities becomes critical. Though an academician may have a great deal of responsibility for the future, he or she also has a personal life that is equally essential, and there are times when his role becomes extremely vital, therefore he must be able to balance both. Work-life balance is extremely important today and must not be overlooked. They must manage themselves while also considering those who may be affected.

Effective communication; because communication is crucial in all aspects of life, it is critical to consider what, when, and how communications are disseminated. Effective communication determines whether a task succeeds or fails. Because we all know that communication is the key to success, it will play a crucial part.

We all seem to be aware that we live in a very dynamic world that is always evolving. It's possible that this is owing to technological advancements. It could also be attributed to a variety of other factors. As a result, it is critical for an academic leader to act as a change agent and assist everyone in adapting to the changing environment. This will not only assist the individual cope with the shift, but it will also facilitate the change.

Because a leader is someone that everyone looks up to, it is critical that he sets an example for his team. The leader is responsible for leading the team, thus he must ensure that the things he is

doing are able to improve and boost individual and team performance. Because the leader plays such an important part in this, he must ensure that his own performance matches the expected outcomes.

Leading an aged workforce: one of the most important variables in academic leadership is the presence of persons who are getting older. There are a number of persons who are involved in this. One of the most crucial duties is to figure out how to deal with this significant issue. Individuals working and learning must strike a balance between the many levels of a company. To be more successful and long-lasting, the effort must be balanced.

Suggestion

Why is this so important? The reality is that these educational leaders are the backbone of future generations, as they pave the road for future leaders, so their role and responsibilities must be carefully observed. Educational leaders should not just be academics, but also leaders who shape the nation's destiny. An educational leader's responsibilities include more than just teaching; they also include a variety of additional responsibilities.

Conclusion:

Teacher educators should take on the responsibility of not only academics but also leaders who will shape the nation's future. In a dynamic world where time and things change, an educationalist must understand and appreciate the changing demands of the world, since this is both crucial and necessary for adapting to changes in the organisation and the globe. Understanding and making those changes possible is critical for a leader, particularly an educator. Maintaining a balance between personal and professional life, or more accurately, a work-life balance, will assist him or her in getting things done quickly.

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